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Magnetic nano-Fe₃O₄@TiO₂/Cu₂O core-shell composite: An efficient novel catalyst for the regioselective synthesis of 1,2,3-triazoles using a click reaction

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Abstract

A magnetic nano-Fe₃O₄@TiO₂/Cu₂O core-shell composite, optimized for the loading amount of Cu₂O, was successfully prepared and fully characterized by analyzing FT-IR, XRD, XPS, FEG-SEM, EDS, and VSM data. The catalytic activity of the nano-Fe₃O₄@TiO₂/Cu₂O core-shell composite was examined in a classical one-pot and three-component reaction of terminal alkynes, benzyl halides, and sodium azide in water that was observed to proceed smoothly and completed in good yields with high regioselectivity. The catalyst was conventionally recovered using an external magnet and was reused in at least five successive runs without an appreciable loss of activity.

Keywords

Catalyst activity, Catalysts, Shells (structures), 1,2,3-triazoles, Click reaction, Core-shell composites, Loading amount, Novel catalysts, Regioselectivity, Regioselective synthesis, Terminal alkyne, Three component reactions.